

INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM: A VERITABLE TOOL FOR FRAUD'S PREVENTION AND DETECTION IN NIGERIAN DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS (DMB)

DADA OLUSEGUN DAVID

Department of Accountancy, Federal Polytechnics, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

AKINLEYE GIDEON TAYO

Department of Accounting, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the relationship between internal control system risk assessment and fraud detection and prevention as well as assess the impact of internal control system management climate on fraud detection and prevention at Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. The study followed the concept of descriptive research surveys. It gathered data by using questionnaires as well as secondary sources. The population of this research work includes eighty-nine thousand, two hundred and seventy-five (89,275) staff members in the twenty DMBs listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2019. Purposive sampling technique was adopted in the selection of 84 respondents from Nigeria's 21 deposit money banks as specified on the date consisting of 4 respondents from each bank. There were a total of 84 questionnaires distributed out of which 76 were collected. In the study, basic frequency table, Pearson's coefficient of correlation, and descriptive statistics were used. Proxies of internal monitoring systems are monitor surroundings and risk evaluation. The study findings showed that: there is a significant relationship between the internal control system and the prevention and detection of fraud in Nigerian DMB. The study recommends that: the management of Nigerian DMB should develop and implement a standard internal control system that is strong enough to stand up to fraud wiles in order to promote continuity of operations. Continuous and rigorous training programs should be in place to ensure the liquidity, solvency and ongoing concern of banks and internal auditors in order to gain adequate knowledge of fraud prevention and detection in the Nigerian banking sector.

Keywords: Internal control system, fraud, prevention and detection, risk assessment, control environment, and deposit money banks

1.1 Introduction

The banking institution which serves as a financial intermediary provides a connection between two economic units, that is, the unit of surplus and the unit of deficit. The surplus unit provides the bank with financial resources in the form of deposits, which in turn channels these resources in the form of loans, advances, acquisition, and leases into the deficit unit. With Nigeria's increasingly rising banking industry, bank fraud is also increasing very rapidly and fraudsters have begun using creative methods. The rate at which fraud is committed as revealed over time in the banking sector has brought to the fore the value of a system of internal control in the industry. Today, however, there is no organization in Nigeria that has no preventive measures against the cankerworm, but despite the achievements of these measures, the situation remains unacceptable as fraud, forgery and corruption continue to permeate and pervade every facet of

our national life (Okoye & Gbegi, 2013). What is more troubling is that, amid common outrage at these threats that have stripped us of our ideals, the situation remains peculiar, that it has continued to call the attention of the global community to the degree that Nigeria is portrayed as being fantastically corrupt. Against the context of fraud, the climate of risk assessment and control has been declared a fantastically powerful step in checkmating the danger of fraud. Risk assessment is a term used to describe the overall process or system for determining hazards and risk factors likely to cause harm (hazard identification). If this is evaluated and time measured, constructive steps would have been taken to minimize the eventuality. A monitoring system, also known as the Internal Control Environment, is a concept for financial reporting, internal audit and management of business risks. It refers to the general attitude, knowledge and actions of directors and managers regarding the internal control system and its significance for the implementation of the system

A number of scholarly published studies on the internal control system were conducted in Nigeria as a preventive measure to reduce fraud but very few considered the significance of risk assessment and control environment in fraud prevention and detection. Yu-Tzu, Hanchung, Rainbow and Wuchun (2019) looked at internal monitoring of operations and enforcement using a special Taiwan dataset. The study focused on exploring the connection between the efficiency of internal audit function (IAF) and the organizational and compliance defects in internal control. Apart from the fact that the research was not performed in Nigeria, the main focus was on evaluating the connection between the consistency of the internal audit function (IAF) and the shortcomings in operations and enforcement and control. No priority was given to preventive measures such as climate management and risk assessment. Olaoye and Adebayo (2019) studied forensic accounting as an instrument for the prevention and identification of fraud in Nigeria's deposit money banks. The paper focused on examining the impact of forensic accounting in Nigerian deposit money banks on fraud prevention and detection, and the study was limited to the banks operating in Ekiti State. Meanwhile some of the Deposit Money banks operating in Nigeria do not have branch in Ekiti State. The study also used Forensic Accounting as a method for preventing and detecting fraud and not managing the environment and evaluating the risk. John, Augustine, Kemebradikemor, Anayochukwu and Oluwaseyi (2019) looked into the effects of fraud in Nigeria on DMBs. The research was motivated by the theory of positivist inquiry. Therefore, the study followed a quantitative analysis approach using the technique ex-post facto. Data emerged solely from the annual reports of the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) covering the period from 2006 to 2016. Besides the fact that the research did not give priority to fraud prevention measures such as control system and risk evaluation, studies of this nature would be more powerful if the primary source is viewed side by side. Olayode and Ayeni (2018) analyzed Nigeria's impacts of internal controls on fraud detection and prevention. However, the study studied the relationship between job segregation, system authorization, and the detection and prevention of fraud and not the impact of the internal control system on fraud prevention and detection. Leah and Josiah (2017) sought to investigate the impact of internal controls on the identification and prevention of fraud among Kenyan commercial banks. It was a formidable study but was not performed in Nigeria.

However, Alhassan (2018) has analyzed the internal fraud prevention and detection control measures listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). The data collected were obtained from both primary and secondary sources using annual financial reports and questionnaires for all DMBs listed in Nigeria. Study was carried out similarly by comparison of the internal control measures and DMB fraud. As metaphors for internal regulation, the study also used regulation climate, control behaviors and risk assessment. However, the study found that the impact of risk assessment at Nigerian Deposit Money Banks is not important in the prevention and detection of fraud. This is against the a-priori presumption that needs further research to be done to confirm this. In addition, the study administered its questionnaires at the chosen bank branches and not the head offices. Individual staff may have a personal interest in making the staff conservative with knowledge to minimize their exposure to reputational danger, thus impairing the results.

It is on this premise that this study stands to analyze the impact of the internal control system on the prevention and detection of fraud using the 20 active deposit money banks listed by the NSE as in the Nigerian financial year 2019. The broad objective of this study is to investigate the impact of the internal control system as a genuine tool for the prevention and detection of fraud in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks (DMB) while focusing on the relationship between monitoring the internal control system and detection and fraud prevention in Nigerian DMB.

2.0 Literature Review

Fraudulent Practices in the Banking Sector: One cannot underestimate the crucial function of internal controls in improving banking financial services. With effective internal control structures, the long-term trust of stakeholders-government, manufacturers, investors, consumers in the reporting, transparency and accurate knowledge fields is improved (Ellis & Jordi, 2015). The Committee on Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) (1992) describes internal controls as the mechanism influenced by the board of directors, management and other staff of the agency, structured to provide fair assurance of organizational efficiency and effectiveness, accurate financial reporting, and compliance with relevant laws and regulations. Perhaps the most deadly of all the risks banks face is fraud. The enormity of Nigeria's bank fraud can be inferred from its size, amount and actual loss. A large number of bank frauds are suppressed partly due to the personalities involved, or due to concerns about the negative impact that such disclosure may have on the bank's profile. Customers may lose trust in the bank and this may cause a downturn in its growth. Fraud leads to loss of money that either belongs to the bank or to clients. Such losses may be covered by the earnings for the affected operating period, thereby reducing the amount of profit available to shareholders for distribution. Fraud losses which are borne by the bank's equity resources affect the financial stability of the bank and limit its ability to expand loans and advances for profitable operations. In severe cases, widespread and significant incidences of fraud can lead to failure of a bank. Fraud will increase a bank's operational costs due to the increased expense of installing the equipment required to identify, prevent and protect the money. It also distracts management by devoting precious time to safeguarding its properties from dishonest persons. This unproductive resource diversion

decreases production and low profits which in turn could delay the bank's development. It also results in a declining impact on banks' asset quality (Uchenna, 2013).

Financial Fraud in Banks: According to Okoye and Gbegi (2013), financial fraud in an institution can be divided into three groups committed by the board of directors, departmental heads and other bank employees. Fraud committed by the Board of Directors is referred to as management fraud, while those committed by departmental heads and other bank employees are considered to be condonable fraud and staff fraud, respectively. Condonable or administrative misconduct may be committed by circumventing the internal control system or violating the internal control regulations. Condonable fraud happens when the employee diverts the property given to the employer to improve the employee's efficiency. Management fraud is a deliberate fraud committed by management through significantly misleading financial statements which injures investors and creditors. Management fraud is sometimes referred to as false financial statements. Fakunle (2006) was of the opinion that management fraud is typically committed by the banks' board of directors, which comprises executives, managers and managers. Groups of management fraud victims are investors and creditors and financial statement is the instrument of perpetration. Most times the purpose of managerial fraud is to encourage more shareholders to come and invest in the banking sector.

Perpetrator's Method of Frauds

There is a variety of ways that top management officials and bank employees will perpetrate fraudulent activities. Idowu and Adedokun (2013) highlighted some common methods by which the banks and other organizations can perpetuate fraud:

- i. **Foreign exchange fraud:** According to Ekechi (1990), this is the way in which the employees of a company forge credit letters and other foreign transaction documents which pave the way for the illegal transfer of funds.
- ii. **Cheque kitting:** This is described as a mechanism by which depositors use the time needed for checking to clear without interest payment to receive an unpaid loan.
- iii. **Till borrowing:** Staffers borrow from the till in the form of I Owe You (I.O.U) in the intention of reimbursing it, but this was not achieved finally. So in that sense, fictional entries emerge.
- iv. **Advance fee fraud:** This involves an agent approaching a bank or person with an offer to access large funds at a lower market interest rate on a long-term basis; the so-called source of such funds is not clearly known as the only way to access it is through the agent who must obtain a fee or reward "in advance" as soon as the agent receives the fee, the agent disappears into the thin air and the facility never come through.
- v. **Computer fraud:** For a long time computer frauds can remain undetected. It may take the form of programmed or device package manipulation, and even hacking / breaking through a remote sensor into the system.

- vi. **Account opening fraud:** This is known as the usual fraudulent activity on the part of staff and customers to open current and banking accounts using false documents to or from which fabricated transactions are carried.
- vii. **Money transfer fraud:** Money transfer services are means through which the funds concerned are transferred to or from a bank to a beneficiary account at any stage in the world, in compliance with the bank customers' instructions.
- viii. **Counterfeit securities:** This is regarded as the new photographic printing equipment which has significantly enabled offenders to replicate forged instruments of high quality. The document may be entirely falsified stock or bonds as loan collateral, other falsified objects such as treasury notes and bankers' acceptances may be submitted to bank for redemption.

Concept of Internal Control

Internal control is the entire system of controls, financial or otherwise defined by management, with the goal of ensuring, as far as possible, the quality and reliability of records, operating the business in an orderly manner and safeguarding the properties of the company, its purpose being to avoid or identify fraud and errors early. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision has established the internal control structures to ensure prudence and stability in the financial system. The assumption that credit is a significant contributing factor to these failures is reinforced by anecdotal data from previous bank failures and also the recent financial crisis. Banks benefit from converting their liabilities into assets, so an incentive is sought for optimum risk benefit behaviour, but bank managers owe a duty of care to their directors (Ellis & Jordi, 2015).

Component of Internal Control System

The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) (1994) was of the opinion that the internal control structure of banks must have the following components for quality and effectiveness in banking operations:

- i. **Control environment:** The organization's control system sets the tone. Control climate considerations include honesty, ethical standards and bank workers competency. Control framework provides the entire system with consistency and order. There are several variables which should represent the control climate. The banking system should show solid ethical principles. This is complicated because there are different issues, rewards and temptations on different parties and shareholders. The methodology and operating style of management cannot be overruled in terms of internal control, because it has a direct effect on fraud detection and prevention.
- ii. **Risk assessment:** Risk assessment denotes the detection, examination, and management of risks from external and internal sources that an entity faces. Risk evaluation is highly important for aim controls. Since internal control is a complex system (continuously evolving economic and operational conditions), risk management

processes are often subject to adjustments and adaptations. Proper setting of targets is a requirement for successful risk management. The risk evaluation looks at internal as well as external risks. The people of the entity; the ideology and organizational style of management; the manner in which management assigns authority and responsibility, and organizes and develops its staff.

Internal Control Requirement

The Consolidated Code of the Turnbull Committee on Corporate Governance (2003), as cited in Adedeji (2012), held that the following basic criteria had to be met by an appropriate internal control system:

- i. Provide guidance to assist banks to implement the requirements in the Code relating to internal control issues
- ii. Make the board maintain a sound system of internal control to safeguard shareholders' investment and the bank's assets
- iii. Mandate the directors, at least on an annual basis, conduct a review of the effectiveness of the group's system of internal control and should report to shareholders that they have done so. The review should cover all controls, including financial, operational and compliance controls and risk management.

Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2004) went further to explain that companies which do not have an effective and functioning internal control system should from time to time review their financial statement to give a true and clear picture of the state of such banks either unquoted banks or quoted banks.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for the present study is depicted in fig. 2.1 below

Fig 2.1: Internal Control System vis-à-vis Bank Fraud

Source: Author Design (2019)

The Fig 2.1 above depicts the interconnectivity between internal control system and bank fraud which is expected to be deterred by the assessment of the organization's risks and their mitigations as well as the control of the environment where the organization is situated

Theories

Fraud Triangle Theory

The theory of fraud Triangle identifies three key factors that must be present in any situation of fraud: perceived threat, incentive, and rationalization. Fraud cannot occur in the absence of the aforementioned elements and the severity of the fraud would depend on the strength of the elements listed above. Sometimes pressure involves personal circumstances which create a demand for more money; such circumstances could include vices such as drug use or gambling, or simply life events such as a job-losing spouse. Other times, pressure comes from on-the-job problems; unrealistic performance targets can provide the motive for fraud. They may also be non-financial motivators. Opportunity is generated by lax internal controls, poor management supervision and/or the use of one's own position and authority. Chance is the opportunity to overcome regulation over fraud. Rae and Subramanian (2008) warn that incentive relates to an employee's capacity and power to understand and take advantage of the vulnerabilities of the organizational structure by allowing for fraud. Public Accounts Auditor (2011) concluded that the use of one's power and authority to commit fraud occurs on several occasions when internal controls are weak or non-existent, or where there is insufficient management oversight. The chances of committing fraud are improved by reducing the size resulting in a shortage of workers. The Lebanese Association of Certified Public Accountants (2009) argued that rationalizations involve compensating for being underpaid or substituting a due but not earned bonus. Rationalization is hard to note, since the fraud perpetrator's mind is not understandable. Individuals who commit fraud have a clear mind-set to explain or excuse their fraudulent acts (Hooper and Pornelli, 2010).

Fraud Diamond Theory

Wolf and Hermanson (2004) presented the model theory of diamond fraud. Wolf et al., (2004) introduce fourth "capabilities" component to the three factor triangle theory of fraud. The theorists were of the opinion that without the right individual with the right skills executing the fraud information, many frauds would not have happened. Furthermore, Wolf et al., (2004) suggested four observational characteristics for engaging in fraudulent activities: authoritative role or function within an organization; ability to grasp and manipulate accounting processes and internal control; trust that he / she will not be identified or, if captured, that he / she will easily get out of it. And last but not least, the ability to cope with the tension generated inside and otherwise good person while he or she is committing wrongdoing. In other words, allowing the system as a whole to function as proposed in its attempt to block any sort of laxity in the system is very important.

Empirical Review

Yu-Tzu, Hanchung, Rainbow, and Wuchun (2019) studied internal monitoring of operations and enforcement using a special Taiwan dataset. The paper looked at the relationship between the consistency of internal audit feature (IAF) and organizational and enforcement defects in internal control. All data required for the financial statements are collected from the database of the Taiwan Economic Journal (TEJ). 3658 companies were observed with observations for the year ended in 2005 to 2007. After removing observations in the financial sector (157 observations), those with missing data for internal audit results (142 observations), and those with missing data for control variables (19), a final sample of 3340 company-year observations was identified. Much of the results come from the electronic industry (56.6%), followed by the chemical industry (6.1%) and the electrical machinery industry (6%), which is proportional to the population. The findings indicated that a larger internal audit team could boost the internal audit performance for both operations and enforcement, while the competency of internal auditors is positively correlated with the efficacy of internal compliance management, but not in operations.

John, Augustine, Kemebradikemor, Anayochukwu and Oluwaseyi (2019) looked into the effects of fraud in Nigeria on DMBs. The research was motivated by the theory of positivist inquiry. Therefore, the thesis followed a quantitative analysis approach using the technique *ex-post facto*. Data were collected from annual reports of the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) covering the period 2006 to 2016. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was used after following major regression assumptions to estimate the effect of the fraud on DMBs. It was found that the overall amount of fraud was negligible, while it had a negative effect on the performance of DMBs; the number of cases identified had a major and positive impact on the performance of DMBs and finally it was discovered that the overall workers involved also had a negative impact on the results. Thus, the study concluded that Nigeria's production of DMBs was influenced by the effect of fraud in the bank sector. Regulation and oversight of DMBs should be more stringent, that is, the CBN and NDIC should tighten their hold in controlling and overseeing to reduce the growing incidence of fraud.

Alhassan (2018) analyzed the internal fraud prevention and detection control measures listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) at Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). The data collected were obtained from both primary and secondary sources using annual financial reports and questionnaires for all DMBs listed in Nigeria to respond. The study was carried out primarily through regression of the internal control measures and fraud in DMBs. Proxies for internal control mechanisms are monitoring surroundings, risk evaluation and control practices. By comparison, the vector for fraud prevention and identification is discretionary accruals. The study found that control climate, risk evaluation, and monitoring practices have a negative effect on fraud detection and prevention (discretionary accruals). However, the risk assessment effect isn't important. Therefore, it was proposed that the management and internal control systems currently run by DMBs in Nigeria be updated to make it strictly compliant with IFRS requirements and guidelines. This can also be assisted by the implementation of forensic

auditing and verification in order to make criminals not only responsible for their acts but also subject to legal prosecution.

Olayode and Ayeni (2018) analyzed Nigeria's impacts of internal controls on fraud detection and prevention. Specifically, the research explored the relationship between job segregation, system authorization and identification and prevention of fraud. The normal least square model estimation technique was used to evaluate the relationship between the explanatory and the dependent variable. The analysis utilized primary data derived from a standardized questionnaire. Study findings showed that device authorization exhibits a substantial joint relationship with identification and prevention of fraud given determination coefficient (R^2) of 0.281. The study recommended allowing adequate system authorization as an internal control system procedure to avoid or detect the element of fraud.

Leah and Josiah (2017) sought to investigate the impact of internal controls on the identification and prevention of fraud among Kenyan commercial banks. The thesis has followed an explanatory approach for the analysis. The research population was all 43 commercial banks that worked during the study time in Kenya. The study carried out a survey on all 43 commercial banks. Primary data was used in the study. An ordinary linear regression model was used. The regressions were performed using version 20 of the social sciences statistical package (SPSS). The results of the regression showed that there was a negative and important relationship between control over reconciliation and prevention and identification of fraud levels. The findings have showed that there is a negative and significant relationship between regulation of financial governance and level of prevention and detection of fraud whereas the relationship between reporting and budget control and level of prevention and detection of fraud has been positive and significant. The study suggested that commercial banks should more often reconcile their accounts in order to reduce the cases of more incidences of frauds. The study also suggests that commercial banks introduce better financial governance control mechanisms through more regular meetings between risk management committee members and the finance and investment committee as well. Another recommendation from the study is that commercial banks can minimize budget variances by better reporting and budgetary control measures as it will reduce cases of frauds

Methodology

Study population are the staff members of Nigeria's twenty-one deposit money banks. Questionnaire is the main investigative instrument for this work. Using purposeful sampling. Questionnaires were given to eighty-four (84) respondents, but they were filled out by seventy-six (76) respondents, representing 90.48 percent, which is considered representative. The responses were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

For their validity and reliability, the questionnaire that was used to assess the effect of the internal control system on fraud prevention and detection was subjected to pretest. The test re-

test corresponded to the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient as follows for each of the instruments used:

Table 3.1: Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

Variables	Measuring Scale	Cronbach's alpha	References
Internal Control System	Control Environment Monitoring Activities Risk Assessment	0.863	Idris (2014)
Fraud Prevention and Detection	Control Environment Monitoring Activities Risk Assessment	0.791	Gupta and Bansal (2012)

Source: Compiled from Idris (2014) and Gupta et al. (2012)

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Results

The researcher drew a sample of eighty-four (84) using purposive sampling techniques among the banks' supervisory staff. That is, four (4) respondents from each of the twenty-one (21) DMBs in Nigeria (Line Managers, Logistics Managers, Desk Customer Officers and Marketing Managers); of the eighty-four questionnaires that were issued, 76 were filled out, returned and used for the research work. The percentage of the questionnaire returned is $76/80 * 100 = 91\%$. Below are the analyses of the responses: The gender distribution shows that thirty-one (40.49%) were Male out of the seventy-six of the respondents and forty-five (59.21%) were female. The results showed that female were more than their male counterparts that fill the questionnaire among the respondents at the supervisory level of banks. The age distribution revealed that six (7.9%) of the respondents were between 25-30 years, nine (11.1%) were between 31-35years, sixteen (21.06%) were between 36-40 years, twenty-one (25.9%) of the respondents were between 41-45years, twenty-one (27.64%) were between 46-50 years while thirteen respondents (16%) were above 51 years. The results indicated that more youth were more at the supervisory level of the bank. The Educational background showed that thirty-five (43.2%) of the total respondents possessed professional certificates such as ICAN and CIBN. Thirty-five, (43.2%) held HND/B.Sc. certificates and eleven (13.6%) had Postgraduate certificates. This implies that all of the respondents had the necessary qualifications that could prompt an objective opinion on the subject matter.

Table 4.1: Demographic Distribution

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender Distribution		
Male	31	40.79
Female	45	59.21
Total	76	100.0
Age Distribution		
25-30 Years	6	7.9
31-35 Years	9	11.85
36-40 Years	16	21.06
41-45 Years	21	27.64
46-50 Years	10	13.16
51 Years and Above	13	17.11
Total	76	100.0
Marital Status		
Married	55	67.9
Single	26	32.1
Total	81	100.0
Qualification:		
ICAN/CIBN	35	43.2
HND/B.Sc.	35	43.2
POSTGRADUATE	11	13.6
Total	81	100.0

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

Control environment of internal control system does not have significant effect on detection and prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs.

Table 4.3: Estimated of effect of control environment and detection/prevention of fraud

Variables	Coeff.	Std. err.	t-value
Control environment	0.757	0.035	21.338*
(Constant)	-0.233	.988	-0.36
N = 81			
F = 455.300			
R-Squared = 0.923			

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

To test this hypothesis, the respondents' scores on the two variables, control of internal control system and detection/prevention of fraud were computed and subjected to simple regression

analysis. The results as indicated in table 4.3 and was found to be insignificant (0.923) showing that control environment of internal control system have insignificant effect on fraud detection/prevention in Nigerian DMBs. In other words, fraud detection/prevention is not influenced by control environment of internal control system in Nigerian DMBs. R-square showed that control environment of internal control system caused about (0.852) variance in fraud detection/prevention. Accordingly, an estimated 85.2% of fraud detection/prevention (dependent variable) of fraud detection/prevention is accounted for by control environment of internal control system (independent variable) while 14.8% is explained by the stochastic in the model. Sequel to the results, null hypothesis is rejected while alternative hypothesis accepted. Internal control system was also found to have a positive and significant effect ($\beta = 0.757$, $t = 21.338$) on detection/prevention of fraud of the sampled DMBs in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Risk assessment of internal control system does not have significant effect on detection and prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs.

Table 4.4: Estimated effect of risk assessment and prevention of fraud

Variables	Coeff.	Std. err.	t-value
Risk Assessment	1.970	0.043	46.251*
(Constant)	-3.755	0.531	-7.070
N = 81			
F =2139.150			
R-Squared = 0.964			

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

To test this hypothesis, the respondents' scores on two variables, risk assessment of internal control system and prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMB were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. The results as indicated in table 4.4 found risk assessment of internal control system to be significant at (0.982,) showing that risk assessment of internal control system has insignificant effect on detection/prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs. That is, detection/prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs is equally not influenced by risk assessment of internal control system. R-square showed that risk assessment of internal control system caused about (0.964) variance in prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs. In other words, an estimate of 96.4% of prevention of fraud in Nigerian commercial banks (dependent variable) is accounted for by risk assessment (independent variable) while 3.6% is explained by the stochastic in the model. Consequently, null hypothesis is while alternative hypothesis is accepted. The under standardized and standardized beta co-efficient of risk assessment are 1.970 and 0.982 respectively with $t= 46.252$ and ($p= 0.000 < 0.05$). The result showed a positive relationship between risk assessment of internal control system and prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs indicating that it is not significant. Null hypothesis is therefore rejected while alternative hypothesis is embraced.

Discussion of findings

The first hypothesis that the control environment of the internal control system has no substantial impact on fraud detection and prevention in Nigerian DMBs has been subjected to statistical analysis using simple regression analysis at a meaning level of 0.05. The result showed that in Nigerian DMBs there was a good and positive relationship between internal control system management environment and fraud detection / prevention. It dismissed the null hypothesis thus accepting alternative hypothesis. The finding is in agreement with Philip, Ishmael and Joseph (2014) who submitted that as a part of the banks' internal control systems in Ghana, there were strong controls in the control process. The variable was highly rated with an average mean of 4.72 among respondents. For the second hypothesis which is risk evaluation, score was determined. The findings indicated that the risk assessment of the internal control system has no major impact on the identification and prevention of fraud in Nigerian DMBs using items in the (questionnaire) research instrument. Using regression analysis this score was subject to statistical analysis. The result suggested that there is a positive connection between internal control system risk assessment and bank fraud. It dismissed the null hypothesis thus supporting the alternative hypothesis. Findings trend along the same path with Alhassan (2018) which found that control system internal control measures, risk assessment, and control practices have a detrimental effect in identifying and preventing fraud (discretionary accruals). It then concluded that risk assessment has no major impact.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study revealed that the design of internal control has gone a long way in curbing the threat of fraud in the banking sector in Nigeria, leading to an increase in the banking sector's corporate performance. Conclusively, it is impossible to undermine the importance of any organization's internal control department, especially banks. Based on the study findings, the management of each Nigerian DMB should develop and implement a standard internal control system that is robust enough to stand up to the wiles of fraud in order to encourage continuity of operations and ensure the banks' definition of liquidity, solvency and ongoing concern. Internal auditors should have ongoing and comprehensive training programs, in order to obtain the sufficient knowledge in fraud prevention and detection in the Nigerian DMB.

References

- Adetula, S. L. & Amupitan, M. D. (2018). Whistle Blowing as a Tool for Combating the Menace of fraud, Forgery and Corruption in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research, Social & Management Sciences*, 4(3), 31 – 49.
- Adedeji, D. B. (2012). Evaluation of Corporate Governance Influence on Internal Control System: A Case Study of Selected Banks in South Western, Nigeria. *Management*, 2(5), 188-192.
- Alhassan, H. (2018). Fraud Detection and Internal Control Measures in Deposit Money Banks Listed on the NSE. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, 1(4), 43 – 54.
- Akani, F. N. & Akaninyene, O. U. (2015). Determinants of Effective Internal Control System in Nigerian Banks. *International Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 142-151.

- Alawiye, A. (2015). The banking reform agenda: the imperatives for corporate governance in a banking environment. *The Nigerian Banker*, 15(2), 11-17.
- Barr, R. H. (2007). A case study in fraudulent financial reporting. Elliot Marketing Inc. Retrieved 16/07/2015 from www.bobbar.biz/Elliot.
- Batra, L. (1992). *Auditing*. New Delhi; Tata Mcgraw Hill Publishing.
- COSO (1994). *Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission on Internal Control & Integrated Framework (COSO) (ICIF)*, 1994.
- Ekechi, A. O. (1990). *Fraud and Forgeries: Causes, Type and Prevention*; paper presented at the National Seminar on Book Audit, Organized by ICAN, Lagos.
- Ellis, K. A & Jordi, M. G. (2015). Effect of internal controls on credit risk among listed Spanish Banks *Journal of OmniaScience* 1, 2(1), 357-389.
- Fakunle, B. (2006). *Audit Companion Practice and Revision Kit*, 2nd Edition. Lagos: F. B. Ventures: 190-207.
- Hooper, M. J. & Pornelli, C. M. (2010). Detering and detecting financial fraud: A platform for action. *Kuwait Arabian Journal*, 2(2), 1-14
- Idowu, A. & Adedokun (2013). Internal Control System on Fraud Detection: Nigeria Experience. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 13(5), 141-152.
- Leah, N. K. & Josiah, A. (2017). Effect of internal controls on fraud detection and prevention among commercial banks in Kenya, 2(1), 52 -68.
- Magu, J. K. (2016). Influence of internal control systems on financial performance of Kenya farmers association limited. *International journal of economics, commerce and management*, 4(4), 784-800.
- Morris J. (2011). The Impact of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems on the Effectiveness of Internal Controls over Financial Reporting. *Journal of Information Systems*, 25(1), 129 - 157.
- Okoye, E. I. & gbegi, D. O. (2013). An evaluation of the effect of fraud and related financial crimes on the Nigerian economy. *Kuwait chapter of Arabian journal of business and management review* 2(7), 1-11.
- Olayode & Ayeni (2018). Internal Control System and Fraud Detection and Prevention in Nigeria: Evidence from Ondo State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research Social & Management Sciences*, 4(12), 91-100.
- Onanuga, A. T. & Oshinloye, M. O. B. (2012). An empirical analysis of occupational frauds in the Nigerian Banking Industry, 1991 -2008. *Journal of Banking*, 6 (1), 1 – 18.
- Oyedeki, R. O. (2015). Internal Control Systems and the Integrity of Bursary Units in Nigerian Universities. *International Journal in Research and Business Management* 3(6), 21-26.
- Rae, K. & Subramaniam, N. (2008). Quality of Internal Control Procedures. Antecedents and moderating effect on organizational justice and employee fraud. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 23(2), 104-124.
- Uchenna, C. (2013). Impact of Fraud and Fraudulent Practices on the Performance of Banks in Nigeria. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*. 15 (1), 13-22.
- Woolf, E. (1997). The effects of computerized accounting system on auditing process: a case study of Mtwara district council (mdc) (Doctoral Dissertation, Mzumbe University).

Yu-Tzu, C., Hanchung, C., Cheng, Rainbow K. & Wuchun, C. (2019). **The impact of** internal audit attributes on the effectiveness of internal control over operations and compliance. JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMICS, Elsevier, 15 (1), 1-19.

List of the Staff in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks as at 30th June, 2019

S/No	Bank	No of Staff	Source
1	Access Bank Plc	6,340	Half Year 2019 Results Presentation to Investors and analysts as at Sept., 2019.
2	Fidelity Bank Plc	2,908	Fidelity Bank H12019 Audited Financial Results.
3	First City Monument Bank Plc	5000	http://www.fcmb.com
4	First Bank Nigeria Limited	8,992	Press release, 29th July, 2019, announcement of unaudited results for the six months ended 30th June, 2019.
5	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	3,556	June 2019 Audited half year report.
6	Polaris Bank Plc	1336	https://www.linkedin.com/company/polaris-bank-l
7	Union Bank of Nigeria Plc	7,000	https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/careers/companies/top-banks-in-nige
8	United Bank of Africa Plc	12,500	https://www.ubagroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/UBA-plc-investor-presentation
9	Zenith Bank Plc	6,600	Zenith Bank Interim Report- 30 th June, 2019.
10	Citibank Nigeria Limited	10,000	2018 Annual Report
11	Ecobank Nigeria Plc	15930	https://www.cbn.gov.ng/Out/2019/RSD/2018%20AR%20KAMA1.pdf
12	Heritage Bank Limited	4000	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heritage_Banking_Company_Limited
13	Keystone Bank Limited	2089	https://www.owler.com/company/keystonebankng
14	Stanbic Ibtc Bank Plc	4,000	Press Release Lagos, Nigeria, 17 September,2019
15	Standard Chartered Bank Limited	900	http://www.sc.com.ng
16	Sterling Bank Plc	3657	http://www.sterling.ng
17	Unity Bank Plc	1,734	http://www.nse.com.ng
18	Wema Bank Plc	1317	http://www.owler.com
19	Suntrust Bank Nigeria Ltd	158	Suntrust 2018 Annual Report
20	Providus Bank	250	http://ng.linkedin.com
	Total Number of Staff	89, 275	